

Cinema Ticket Selling System

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How to cite this paper: San San Lwin | Win Win Maw "Cinema Ticket Selling System" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-5, August 2019, pp.1813-1817, <https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd26698>

IJTSRD26698

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Cinema being the modern society social, economic and cultural influence is a serious incident, the most popular out-of-Home is one of the cultural activities. Through Cinema Ticket Selling System offer a comprehensive solution for ticket selling. In Theater Form, easy to understand, easy to use and fast for user that provides point-and-click of the service is Cinema Ticket Selling System. Cinema Ticket Selling System helps in managing the database for storing and retrieving required information about movies schedules, movies collections and ticket sale. This system basically manages the cinema ticket selling process of a multiplex; providing an interface to the user to buy movie tickets in a more easy way. In the system admin can use cinema ticket selling system, to insert and delete data such as movie description, movie schedule will update and can also report day-to-day aspects of selling makes such as daily, weekly, monthly reports. C# is the first component oriented language in the C and C++ family of language which has a lot of advantages. Database is easy to create and understand using Microsoft Access, and then, which is created the C# programming code. In this system, Cinema Ticket Selling System are created by developer, which is need to understand the C# programming, Microsoft access database, which is to know how it is work in Microsoft Visual Studio and the user will be able to create their own application software easily.

2. SYSTEM DESIGN OF CINEMA TICKET SELLING SYSTEM

This system describes Cinema description and is designed by C#. C# is widely-used open source general-purpose programming language. C# is easy to learn and can connect

ABSTRACT

Cinema Ticket Selling System is developed for Cinema. Database is designed in Microsoft Access. It is designed to manage the record about movies schedule, movies collection, and ticket sales' report. Cinema Ticket Selling System helps in managing the database for storing and retrieving required movies information. In this system basically manages the cinema ticket selling process of a multiplex; providing an interface to the user to buy movie tickets in a more easy way. In this system, the admin can use cinema ticket selling system, to update movie description and schedule and then can also calculate ticket sales report. This system is described Cinema Ticket Selling System using C# and it can be seen that the advantages of visual studio. It can be written by using C, C++, and Java programming language. The testing of this system should prove that the organizations to do their work in a more appropriate form of many aspects of computerized system.

KEYWORDS: Cinema Ticket Selling System, C#

1. INTRODUCTION

Cinepax is the first cinema in Pakistan that is providing a world class movie-going experience to people of Pakistan by building a state of the art movie theatre in urban cities. Cinepax is the first Cineplex Company in Pakistan that is building the country's first nationally branded Cineplex chain. Total area of Cinepax is 33225 Square feet, Total Cinema screens are 5 and the halls are equipped with total 1400 seats.

many databases. In that, Microsoft Access is the most popular database. It is very easy to use and data can insert, update and delete.

There are two portions in the proposed system design. These are the user site and administrator site. Firstly, the administrator must enter the administrator's name and password. There is password detection to valid the administrator who is authorized in that service. If the name and password is incorrect, is not allowed to enter the system and will be shown a denied message. If these facts are correct, the admin gets the permission as an administrator. As database of this system can be added, updated and deleted in the administrator site, this system is always up-to-date. So, the administrator can handle the database of the system and do anything about the movies descriptions. Also, the admin can search the name of the movie and add the movie schedule and can update the number of seats. The System Design of the Admin will be shown in figure 2.1.

In the user site, when the user does not have user account, the admin gives the permission user account. Admin can make the new user account if users want to enter membership. Any user can do the Sell Form and select the movies times, movies names and theater names as customer choose and print the tickets. The user does not allow entering all form. And if the user enters, other form except Sell Form the system will show the denied messages. The System Design of the User Site will be shown figure 2.2.

A system design document is drafted that details the specific business processes that will be modeled and streamlined

using the proposed software solution. System design is the process of defining the architecture, modules, interface and data for a system to satisfy specified requirements. System design could be seen as the application of the systems theory to product development.

Figure: 2.1. System Design for Admin

Figure: 2.2. System Design for User

3. OVERVIEW OF CINEMA TICKET SELLING SYSTEM

Cinema Ticket Selling System is computerized by various attributes and properties of the movies that help to maintain and manage records through this mini-thesis.

Movie's ID: All the movies are assigned a unique code which helps in identifies the record of each movie.

Movie's Name: It gives opportunity to the user to select the movie by recognizing through its name.

Movie's Day, Date, Time and Screen: It tells about the day along with the time and screen on which the movie will be

showed. This helps in telling the customer about the timings of the movie shows.

Ticket's Price: It tells about the price of the movie. It describes the ticket assigned to that movie and also the start and end ticket number of that ticket sell.

Ticket Sold: It tells the total number of the tickets being sold for a specific movie.

4. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SYSTEM

Login Form

In Login Form, user name and password are filled and also classified the admin and staff. Login Form, is shown in figure 4.1. If the user name and password is incorrect, the denied messages will show.

Figure: 4.1. Login Form

Admin and Staff Login Form

If the adman's user name and password entered, the admin can do anytime about the movie schedule, movie collection, ticket sales and update the seat.

Figure 4.2 (a) Admin Login Form

Figure 4.2 (b) Staff Login Form

If user name and password is staff account, can't do anything about the movie schedule, movie collection and ticket sale. If staff used other form, the admin control form and the denied message will show as shown in figure 4.2 (c).

Figure 4.2 (c) Denied Messages

row and column), Report Form (which has to calculate about the ticket sale) and Setting Form (which has to see user account permission). The Main Form is shown in figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3 Main Form

Main Form

If user name and password correct, the main form will be seen. In Main form include Sell Form (which has to use reception), Ticket Setup Form (which has to fill about movie by admin), Theater Form (which has to insert about seat's

Ticket Setup Form

In Ticket Setup Form contain No., Movie Title, Theater Name, Start Date and End Date will be shown in figure 4.4.

No	Title	Theater	Start Date	End Date
1	Ada, Awa & Dta	Theater One	Tuesday, October 9, 2018	Monday, October 15, 2018
2	Nin Say Yin	Theater Two	Tuesday, October 9, 2018	Monday, October 15, 2018
3	From Bangonk To Mandalay	Theater Three	Tuesday, October 9, 2018	Monday, October 15, 2018

Figure 4.4 Ticket Setup Form

And then, Add Movie Form can also contain to manage the selected movie, theater name, and data related with movies. In this form, the admin can view and delete information about schedule which includes, start date and end date, movie name, time and theater number.

Add Movie

Movie Name:

Theater:

Start Date:

Numbers of day to show:

Same as Default Show Time

No.	Start Time	End Time
1	10:00 AM	11:30 AM
2	12:00 PM	09:30 PM
3	03:00 PM	01:30 PM
4	05:00 PM	05:30 PM
5	08:00 PM	10:30 PM

Add More

Figure 4.5 Add Movie Form

Theater Form

In Theater Form, the admin can control the number of seat which seats are broken, which seats aren't used and which seats are sold which the default color as shown in figure 4.6.

TheaterForm

Screen

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
A	A-1	A-2	A-3	A-4	A-5	A-6	A-7	A-8	A-9	Way	A-10	A-11	A-12	A-13	A-14	A-15	A-16	A-17	A-18	A-19	A-20
B	B-1	B-2	B-3	B-4	B-5	B-6	B-7	B-8	B-9	Way	B-10	B-11	B-12	B-13	B-14	B-15	B-16	B-17	B-18	B-19	B-20
C	C-1	C-2	C-3	C-4	C-5	C-6	C-7	C-8	C-9	Way	C-10	C-11	C-12	C-13	C-14	C-15	C-16	C-17	C-18	C-19	C-20
D	D-1	D-2	D-3	D-4	D-5	D-6	D-7	D-8	D-9	Way	D-10	D-11	D-12	D-13	D-14	D-15	D-16	D-17	D-18	D-19	D-20
E	E-1	E-2	E-3	E-4	E-5	E-6	E-7	E-8	E-9	Way	E-10	E-11	E-12	E-13	E-14	E-15	E-16	E-17	E-18	E-19	E-20
F	F-1	F-2	F-3	F-4	F-5	F-6	F-7	F-8	F-9	Way	F-10	F-11	F-12	F-13	F-14	F-15	F-16	F-17	F-18	F-19	F-20
G	G-1	G-2	G-3	G-4	G-5	G-6	G-7	G-8	G-9	Way	G-10	G-11	G-12	G-13	G-14	G-15	G-16	G-17	G-18	G-19	G-20
H	H-1	H-2	H-3	H-4	H-5	H-6	H-7	H-8	H-9	Way	H-10	H-11	H-12	H-13	H-14	H-15	H-16	H-17	H-18	H-19	H-20
I	I-1	I-2	I-3	I-4	I-5	I-6	I-7	I-8	I-9	Way	I-10	I-11	I-12	I-13	I-14	I-15	I-16	I-17	I-18	I-19	I-20
J	J-1	J-2	J-3	J-4	J-5	J-6	J-7	J-8	J-9	Way	J-10	J-11	J-12	J-13	J-14	J-15	J-16	J-17	J-18	J-19	J-20

Figure: 4.6. Theater Form

As chosen new button, the admin can insert the Theater Name, Sort Order (A to Z (or) Z to A), and Left to Right of seats arrange. When the admin can use the default price and time, the admin can select the checkbox.

NewTheaterForm

Theater ID:

Theater Name:

Sort Order:

Left To Right:

Same as Default Price

Same as Default Show Time

Figure 4.7 New Theater Form

And then, also include Add Row Form by clicking add button. In this form, admin can insert number of seats by classified row and column and walkway (which is path for walking along). Prices are standardized with different color.

Figure 4.8 Add Row Form

Report Form

In Report Form, admin can calculate ticket sales with Theater name or with Movies name. And can calculate daily, monthly, and yearly income and can show the total income.

Figure 4.9 (a) Report by Theater

Figure 4.9 (b) Report by Movies names

User List Form

In Setting Form can classify the admin account, staff account (which also contains the account's owner name). Admin can update the user account permissions. And then the user can logout.

Figure 4.10 User List Form

Sell Form

The Sell Form can use a place where reception, in sell form will show the one reception form to choose the number of seats, movies names, time and movies information customer wanted.

Figure: 4.11. One Reception Form

In Sell Form also include the Book Seat Form which have to choose the customer wanted movies, number of seats and time. By click Book button, the print will fill out. The Book Seat Form is shown in Figure 4.12.

Figure: 4.12. Book Seat Form

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This system is described Cinema Ticket Selling System using C# and it can be seen that the advantages of visual studio. It can be written by using C, C++, Java programming language. The testing of this system should prove that this system is perfect or the organizations to do their work in a more appropriate form. There are many aspects of this computerized system. The organization is now using this system and by the help of this system their efficiency has been increased. This is also a time saving which can do many things. This system is formed in such a way that it will contain all the latest features. It is more reliable than any other system available for data saving now days. In the future further developments could also be done on it make it more efficient.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author is very grateful to the committee of IJTSRD and editorial board for permitting the study to publish. The author wishes to acknowledge the researchers and writers who wrote and created the journals, books and articles that are of great help to me for my journal. Without them, I would not think of any ideas and could not finish my journal successfully.

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